

1 **Game Performance Assessment Instrument in Physical Education: A**
2 **Systematic Review from 2015 to 2022**

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30 **Game Performance Assessment Instrument in Physical Education:**
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35 Abstract

36 *Background:* The use of the Game Performance Assessment Instruments (GPAI) in
37 schools has increased in recent years. Other instruments have been employed to
38 measure tactical-technical components in sports such as the Game Performance
39 Evaluation Tool. However, it is necessary to consider the context (school or youth
40 sport) for employing each instrument because it is important to consider learners'
41 skill level to adjust the criteria definitions for evaluation.

42 *Purpose:* The objective of this systematic review was to review interventions using
43 the GPAI instrument in the physical education educational field. This study
44 updates the Aguilar et al.'s (2016) systematic review.

45 *Methods:* A systematic search of the literature was conducted across 5 databases
46 (WoS, ERIC, ProQuest, SPORTDiscus, and SciELO) using key words related to
47 the Game Performance Assessment Instrument, Physical Education (Spanish or
48 English), and the Boolean operators "OR" and "AND". The authors conducted a
49 manual search of reviews including instruments evaluating game performance in
50 young people. All searches were exported to Mendeley® software, and duplicated
51 documents were removed. The first level of exclusion criteria was to remove not
52 original articles reading titles and abstracts. The second exclusion criteria were: (1)
53 using GPAI out of PE lessons/fields (i.e., sports training), (2) articles not applying
54 intervention on PE (i.e., theoretical articles or data collection only), and (3)
55 interventions on PE but not using GPAI. The PRISMA guidelines was followed
56 during the process. Finally, the quality of the included articles was measured using
57 the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool.

58 *Results:* 23 papers were identified as meeting the inclusion criteria. The results
59 showed most of the included articles analyzed the influence of pedagogical models
60 on the students' learning. In comparison to previous reviews, there was greater use
61 of this instrument along with the implementation of the models' hybridization that
62 seemed to have better results than the application of one model. Conversely,
63 invasion or net games were evaluated while previous reviews included more sport
64 categories.

65 The most analyzed game components were Decision-Making and Skill execution
66 and most researchers employed indexes of these components despite it could mask
67 the nature of the students' learning. 20 papers used video recordings to evaluate the
68 GPAI but only 12 studies detailed the training time received by expert coders.
69 Also, only one paper used the GPAI with live students, and explained they
70 received a previous training session. Knowledge tests were linked to the GPAI to
71 measure cognitive/physical learning among students.

72 *Conclusions:* The evaluation of game performance and its components has been
73 linked to the application of pedagogical models and within the school context. It is
74 suggested that the GPAI be used with knowledge tests to confirm students'
75 learning acquisition. Moreover, the benefits of using technology can facilitate the
76 implementation of GPAI through standardized software by students and teachers.
77 Future studies should explore the involvement of students in their assessment, use
78 of technology, and different games.

79 Keywords: assessment, game components, learning, sport pedagogy, school
80 context

81 Disclosure statement

82 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

83 **Introduction**

84 Pedagogical enactments of sports-related content, focusing on tactical-technical elements,
85 have witnessed a growing impact within the domain of Physical Education (PE) field
86 (Harvey & Jarrett, 2014; Morales-Belando et al., 2022; Stolz & Pill, 2013). However,
87 evaluating learners' tactical-technical outcomes requires specific attention.

88 Previous works, such as Arias-Estero and Castejón (2014) or Barquero-Ruiz et al.
89 (2020), have reviewed the studies using specific instruments to measure these outcomes
90 on students or players in extracurricular or sports contexts. Several instruments have been
91 employed to measure tactical-technical components in sports such as the Game
92 Performance Evaluation Tool (GPET) (García-López et al., 2013), the system of tactical
93 assessment in Soccer (FUTSAT) (Teoldo et al., 2011) or Game Performance Assessment

94 Instrument (GPAI) (Oslin et al., 1998). However, Gutiérrez-Díaz et al. (2011) concluded
95 that considering the context (school or youth sport) is crucial to employing each
96 instrument because it is necessary to consider learners' skill level to adjust the criteria
97 definitions for evaluation. Therefore, in line with Aguilar et al.'s (2016) review, this
98 study delves into the use of the GPAI as the most employed instrument in PE in recent
99 years (Barquero-Ruiz et al., 2020).

100 Oslin et al. (1998) developed the GPAI to evaluate performance behaviors in
101 tactical problems by choosing and applying appropriate decisions and skills. Moreover,
102 the GPAI was linked to the school context, specifically the Tactical Games model,
103 because teachers could relate teaching and students' learning acquired with this method
104 in a real game context (Griffin & Richard, 2003). In this sense, teachers can evaluate
105 several game components (i.e., decision-making, skill execution, adjust, cover, support,
106 guards/marks, and bases) and game performance and involvement according to the game
107 evaluated (Mitchell et al., 2006). These authors suggested two methods to measure GPAI
108 components: 1-5 the Likert-like method or the tally scoring method.

109 Notwithstanding, authors such as Memmert and Harvey (2008) identified some
110 concerns regarding the use of the GPAI to calculate individual/overall game performance
111 indices, the use of game performance or involvement, and reliability among evaluators.
112 Barquero-Ruiz et al. (2020) also identified some issues related to using instruments to
113 measure tactical-technical learning (e.g., using indexes that masked the results or the
114 employment of instruments in contexts for which they were not validated). These
115 concerns could affect the real assessment of student learning, and recent studies should
116 explore the use of the GPAI in this field. Therefore, the purpose of this manuscript was to
117 review interventions using the GPAI instrument in the educational field (PE) from 2015
118 to 2022. This study updates the preview review by Aguilar et al. (2016).

119 **Method**

120 This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic
121 Reviews and Meta-Analyses guidelines (Page et al., 2021). It was registered in
122 PROSPERO (CODE HERE) to ensure the reliability of the review process.

123 ***Data sources and search strategy***

124 The search strategy was designed considering previous and specific reviews of
125 interventions using the GPAI (e.g., Aguilar et al., 2016). A systematic literature review
126 was conducted between 2015-2022 to explore new trends and years on this topic. The
127 Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, Education Resource Information Center (ERIC),
128 ProQuest, Education Sources, SPORTDiscus, and SciELO databases were searched. The
129 search strategy includes the terms “Game Performance Assessment Instrument” and
130 “Physical Education” (Spanish or English), and the Boolean operators “OR” and “AND”
131 were used.

132 Moreover, the authors conducted a manual search of reviews including
133 instruments evaluating game performance in young people (e.g., Barquero-Ruiz et al.,
134 2020). Despite reviews not providing different from the electronic search using databases,
135 reinforcing the reliability of the searches. Searches were exported to Mendeley® software
136 to let authors perform the review process, guaranteeing its reliability.

137 ***Study selection criteria***

138 First, the duplicated articles were removed. In the first level of exclusion,
139 systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and other not original articles were eliminated. Then,
140 the following exclusion criteria were applied: (1) using GPAI out of PE lessons/fields
141 (i.e., sports training), (2) articles not applying intervention on PE (i.e., theoretical articles
142 or data collection only), and (3) interventions on PE but not using GPAI. Figure 1 shows
143 this process. Articles that were not excluded were selected for quality assessment.

144 ***Quality assessment and data extraction***

145 The PRISMA (2020) checklist assessed the systematic review quality. PRISMA
146 items referred to meta-analysis were not assessed for this review. The quality of the
147 articles selected in this review was evaluated using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool
148 (MMAT) (Hong et al., 2018). It includes several items to evaluate articles according to
149 the methods employed (quantitative or mixed methods in this review). The MMAT
150 evaluates each item as follows: yes (1), cannot tell (0.5), or no (0); and scores were set as
151 low (1-2), medium (3), or high (4–5). Two authors evaluated the articles, and Kappa
152 statistic (κ) was employed to test interrater reliability (Cohen, 1968). Discrepancies were
153 discussed among all the manuscript authors to reach a 100% consensus.

154 According to the data extraction, a standardized form was used to collect the
155 following information from each selected study (see Table 1): author(s) and year of
156 publication; purpose(s) of the article; sample, length of the intervention, and information
157 on the content applied; data collection and variables (including the game elements
158 evaluated using the GPAI); and results and conclusions of the studies.

159 **Results and Discussion**

160 This study aimed to systematically review interventions using the GPAI in
161 education from 2015-2022. Two authors performed all review processes to ensure
162 reliability. The search strategy conducted in the seven databases yielded 197 studies
163 (Figure 1). 41 articles were removed because they were in duplicate or outside the year
164 range. The first level consisted of reading titles and abstracts and screening the type of
165 articles.

166 The second level involved screening the article text to identify the three exclusion
167 criteria mentioned in the methods section. Finally, the quality of the articles was
168 evaluated by two authors ($k= 0.625$; good initial interrater agreement). Most articles were

169 of high or medium quality (96%; Supplemental Table 1). A total of 23 articles were
170 analyzed in depth (see Table 1). According to the information in Table 1, results have
171 been analyzed and discussed.

172 *Purpose/s of the studies*

173 The predominant purpose of the studies in this review was to analyze the
174 suitability of using pedagogical models to improve students' understanding of games.
175 While the GPAI was linked to the Tactical Games model (Griffin & Richard, 2003), the
176 use of the Sport Education model predominated in this review (n=7). The Games-Based
177 Approaches (González-Víllora et al., 2021) were also widely applied along with the
178 GPAI (n=5) (including Teaching Games for Understanding or the Tactical Games). Six
179 articles used hybridizations of models as methodology, and all merged Sport Education
180 with the Step-Game Approach, Teaching Games for Understanding or Teaching Personal
181 and Responsibility. The use of pedagogical models with the GPAI has increased since a
182 review by Aguilar et al. (2016). This review only showed ten studies applying Teaching
183 Games for Understanding, and the other three applied sports education. There was no
184 evidence from studies on the hybridization of pedagogical models. Thus, reinforcing the
185 research by combining different models could provide another way to build model-based
186 practices (González-Víllora et al., 2019).

187 Other studies did not investigate the influence of pedagogical models on students'
188 game performance but rather analyzed the influence of whole-game situations (Macías-
189 Romero et al., 2018), small-sided games (Khalifa et al., 2020; Morales-Belando & Arias-
190 Estero, 2015) or non-linear pedagogy (Gil-Arias et al., 2016). Whole-game situations and
191 small-sided games are crucial when applying game-based approaches (Harvey & Jarrett,
192 2014). Finally, one study analyzed the influence of the Behavioral Ecological model on

193 students' tactical-technical learning by incorporating a motion analysis app (Yu et al.,
194 2021).

195 ***Sample, length of the intervention, and content/s employed***

196 Most of the interventions were applied to 6th to 8th grade (n=13). Kirk &
197 MacPhail (2002) recommended this age being “critical” for players/learners to begin in
198 the tactical understanding of (invasion) games. Conversely, one article focused on the
199 tactical-technical learning of 2nd graders (Puente-Maxera et al., 2020) and two applied to
200 11th graders (Mahedero et al., 2021; Pan et al., 2019), in comparison with Aguilar et al.'s
201 (2016) review, both grades were innovative. Although future studies should increase the
202 GPAI among adolescents at the last age of compulsory education, using this instrument
203 among the youngest graders requires attention. Regardless of grade, the use of the GPAI
204 is widespread in the school context, in line with Barquero-Ruiz et al. (2020), where sixty-
205 six percent of the studies that analyze the GPAI focus on that institutional context.

206 Only two studies assessed the GPAI on wide samples (exceeding 100 students
207 analyzed) (Mahedero et al., 2021; Pan et al., 2019). Therefore, some studies usually
208 indicate obtaining larger samples as prospects (e.g., Araújo et al., 2019), but the
209 evaluation of tactical-technical learning requires an overload of work on the evaluators,
210 so the greater the number of players to be evaluated, the more time it demands. Linked to
211 the demanded time, the length of the implementations ranged from six to 35 sessions,
212 also influenced using pedagogical models as methodologies (Hastie & Mesquita, 2016).

213 According to the content employed, and although the GPAI was designed to
214 assess sports performance in all game categories (Oslin et al., 1998), most studies focused
215 on invasion games (e.g., handball or floorball; n=13). Results agreed with Aguilar et al.
216 (2016) and Arias-Estero and Castejón (2012). Also, net games were the second most
217 analyzed category in the studies reviewed in this work (n=10). Other categories were not

218 analyzed, differing from the results of Arias-Estero and Castejón (2012), who found
219 field/run/score games studies. Future studies should evaluate the use of the GPAI in
220 components of other sports categories to shed light on the lack of information on this
221 topic.

222 *Data collection and variables*

223 This section is crucial to (1) deeply examine the GPAI components evaluated by
224 the researchers, (2) understand how the GPAI was used to evaluate tactical-technical
225 outcomes, and (3) review other instruments employed to measure the variables of each
226 study and their links with the GPAI.

227 *GPAI components analyzed in the studies*

228 Of the seven GPAI components identified by Oslin et al. (1998), the most
229 analyzed were decision-making (22), skill execution (20), and game performance (18).
230 These results were consistent with those reported by Arias-Estero and Castejón (2012)
231 and Barquero-Ruiz et al. (2020), but this study found an increase in the number of studies
232 assessing other components such as support (n=10), game involvement (n=9), cover or
233 guard/mark (n=4), adjust (n=2) and base (n=1).

234 In the evaluated components of the GPAI, most articles employed indexes of
235 these components to transform the results of the measured components into representative
236 numbers (Arias-Estero & Castejón, 2012). However, Memmert and Harvey (2008)
237 identified indexes as a constraint because they mask the nature of the player's learning
238 outcome profile (Barquero-Ruiz et al., 2020), and considered a possible solution to
239 calculate the game performance index and game involvement index to obtain a more
240 consistent value. Moreover, they suggested calculating game involvement indexes for
241 younger ages (4-6 graders) and game performance for older students because of the
242 nature of both components.

243 For this reason, other instruments, such as the GPET, evaluate game performance
244 from a tactical lens and consider the sport tactical and operational principles (García-
245 López et al., 2013), while the FUT-SAT considers the fundamental principles to evaluate
246 soccer (Teoldo et al., 2011). This ecological view could help contextualize students’
247 tactical learning of principles that differ in specific game situations requiring different
248 decision-making. Oslin et al. (1998) did not establish a closed and detailed description
249 because they wanted the GPAI to be an adaptable tool for the needs and conditions of
250 learners, teachers/coaches, and/or the context. 17 articles used self-made (ad-hoc) criteria
251 to determine appropriate/inappropriate behaviors in implementing the GPAI. Among
252 them, four did not detail or exemplify any criteria, and five articles used criteria
253 predefined by others (e.g., Farias et al. (2022) assessed volleyball components based on
254 the criteria of Mesquita et al. (2005)). Finally, Salimin et al. (2020) adapted the GPAI to
255 analyze decision-making in volleyball (open space, closed space, and using skills).

256 The results showed that using the GPAI required adapting the criteria to fit the
257 researcher/teacher’s purposes. Predefined criteria in some articles could be an effective
258 and reliable solution for guiding the assessment of game components in the same game
259 category (Aguilar et al., 2016). As Barquero-Ruiz et al. (2020) recommended, using a
260 description of validated criteria reinforces the reliability and validity of the evaluation
261 process.

262 *Assessment procedure of the GPAI*

263 The GPAI was designed as a versatile tool to evaluate game components by
264 analyzing video recordings or “in-live” (Oslin et al., 1998). 20 studies analyzed the GPAI
265 through video recordings, coding the data of observed disturbances, and/or expert coding
266 without mentioning its use by students. Two studies did not reflect on how the instrument
267 was applied or who used it (Pan et al., 2019; Salimin et al., 2020), and only one study

268 mentioned its use by students in live (Macías-Romero et al., 2018). However, according
269 to students' responses to interviews, Macías-Romero et al. (2018) highlighted
270 improvements in learning attributable to the use of the GPAI. Reciprocal evaluation as a
271 learning tool in PE enables better decision-making (Figueiredo et al., 2008). Oslin et al.
272 (1998) recommended simplifying the GPAI when students were involved in the process
273 as evaluators. Future research should deepen the difference between evaluating it by
274 students or teachers/trained evaluators in student learning.

275 Specifically, Memmert and Harvey (2008) and Oslin et al. (1998) identified the
276 experience and training of evaluators as key elements for ensuring the reliability and
277 validity of the results. This was the main reason most studies in this review evaluated
278 game components via video analysis. More recently, Barquero-Ruiz et al. (2020)
279 highlighted the need to consider variables, such as an evaluator's previous experience and
280 training, when using instruments to assess tactical learning in games. Among the articles
281 included in this review that used video recordings to evaluate the GPAI (n=20), only 12
282 studies detailed the training time received by expert coders (ranging eight-50), and 19
283 included information about inter-observer and/or intra-observer reliability tests to
284 reinforce the reliability of the evaluation process. Macías-Romero et al.'s (2018) study,
285 which used the GPAI with live students, explained they received a previous training
286 session.

287 Mitchell et al. (2006) established 1-5 Likert-like and tally scoring methods to
288 measure GPAI components. In this review, 14 studies reported tally scoring to record
289 effective/effective executions and/or appropriate/inappropriate decisions (e.g., Guijarro et
290 al., 2022). Regarding the use of a Likert-type scale, the method described by Hastie et al.
291 (2013) was mentioned in three articles (e.g., Mahedero et al., 2021). In this line, an article
292 (Macías-Romero et al., 2018) uses a similar method (1-3 Likert-type scale). Finally, the

293 method described in the manual of Derwent et al. (2018) was also used by Farias et al.
294 (2022).

295 In addition, the time taken to evaluate each player is relevant to ensure the
296 measurement of their learning. While Blomqvist et al. (2005) set 10 uninterrupted
297 minutes of observation, Farias et al. (2015) established at least five minutes/player. All
298 studies in this review evaluated video recordings using 10-minute (n=14), 8-minute
299 (n=4), and 5-minute (n=1) recordings.

300 *Using other instruments along with the GPAI to measure or explore students'*
301 *tactical learning*

302 To develop students' game understanding, it is possible to use other pedagogical
303 tools (e.g., questioning or team talks) next to the GPAI (Memmert & Harvey, 2008). The
304 most common combination of instruments used to collect data was the GPAI with game
305 knowledge tests to confirm the acquisition of students' learning of the content applied
306 (n=7). It is convenient to investigate the influence of students' game knowledge on its
307 application to a real game, which is subsequently evaluated using the GPAI. These results
308 align with Figueiredo et al.'s (2008) recommendation of using declarative questionnaires
309 together with the GPAI to better understand students' learning.

310 Conversely, interviews, diaries, focus groups, and expert comments were used to
311 collect qualitative data in eight. These instruments provide in-depth information about
312 students' knowledge. Mixed research designs strengthen conclusions, ensure the
313 discovery of contradictions/similarities among instruments, and deepen the scope of the
314 study (Greene & Caracelli, 2003).

315 ***Main results of the studies included in the review***

316 First, the use of the GPAI was initially linked to game-based approaches (more
317 specifically to the Tactical Games model; Griffin & Richard, 2003). Some interventions
318 using these approaches showed students' improvements in decision-making, skill

319 execution (Mazzardo et al. (2022) found improvements in this component in boys only),
320 cover, support, game performance, and game involvement (e.g., Morales-Belando et al.,
321 2018), while other studies did not find significant differences (e.g., Gouveia et al., 2019).
322 However, better results were obtained when these approaches were applied to PE than
323 technique-oriented approaches (Gouveia et al., 2019), in agreement with Aguilar et al.'s
324 (2016) review. This is because models such as Tactical Games have a greater cognitive
325 impact to select the most appropriate decision, increasing their involvement in the game
326 (Harvey et al., 2009).

327 Second, the use of Sport Education along with GPAI improves students' decision-
328 making (Mahedero et al., 2015), game performance (Puente-Maxera et al., 2020), skill
329 execution (Rocamora et al., 2019), and game involvement (Farias et al., 2018). Using
330 many games during a prolonged season (to consolidate learning), belonging to the same
331 team, and the possibility of performing roles other than players were key elements in
332 achieving the abovementioned improvements (Hastie et al., 2009). However, some
333 studies have shown students with low or moderate skills obtained greater improvements
334 in decision-making, game performance, and game involvement than the more skilled ones
335 (Mahedero et al., 2022). Araújo et al. (2016) concluded this could be due to highest-
336 skilled students obtain high scores in the pretest. It should also be noted that the evolution
337 of game performance and involvement is neither linear nor concurrent (Farias et al.,
338 2019). Individual constraints and sports-specific motor skills also play important roles.
339 Therefore, a certain level of game awareness is necessary to better exploit game
340 possibilities (Renshaw et al. 2010). Considering the intrinsic features of other instruments
341 (e.g., GPET), it could be useful to contextualize/differentiate game situations considering
342 the game operational/tactical principles to reinforce how students make decisions and
343 perform skills.

344 Third, the hybridization between the sports education model and game-based
345 approaches also impacted student learning. Compared to Aguilar et al.'s (2016) review of
346 the use of the GPAI in PE, hybridization among pedagogical models has increased
347 notably in recent years. So, when Sport Education is hybridized with the Step-Games
348 Approach in volleyball, the students improve their game performance, game involvement,
349 decision-making, adjust, and skill execution (Araújo et al., 2016; 2019) and, more
350 specifically, their “serve,” “reception,” and “setting” (Farias et al., 2022).
351 Notwithstanding, when comparing the use of an isolated Games-Based Approach (i.e.,
352 Teaching Games for Understanding) versus its hybridization with Sport Education, the
353 latter showed better results in improving students’ decision-making (Salimin et al., 2020),
354 game performance and game involvement (Guijarro et al., 2022). In this sense, something
355 similar occurred in favor of the hybridization of Teaching Personal and Social
356 Responsibility with the Sports Education, showing improvements in game performance
357 versus its hybridization with the Traditional Teaching (Pan et al., 2019). Therefore,
358 hybridization can reinforce the possibilities of pedagogical models (González-Villora et
359 al., 2019).

360 However, other studies have not employed pedagogical models. The manipulation
361 of task constraints shows improvements in decision-making (Gil-Arias et al., 2016), in
362 line with studies such as Silva et al. (2014), where wider game spaces favored more
363 distance between attackers and defenders and, more time to decide and act. Procedural
364 knowledge (the key to decision-making in the game) improves because of the learning
365 generated by the observation instrument used (GPAI) by the students themselves
366 (Macías-Romero & Otero, 2018). Involving students in the evaluation process is an
367 effective strategy for improving their learning (Figueiredo et al., 2008). Similarly, Yu et
368 al. (2021), all students improved their GPAI scores because the app provided instant

369 feedback-based videos to review and improve their skill execution and game-play.
370 However, verbal interaction and cooperative learning have been suggested to improve
371 tactical understanding (Khalifa et al., 2020). It should be noted that a decrease in the
372 number of players increases Game Involvement but does not affect the components of
373 skill execution, decision-making, defense, and game performance (Morales-Belando &
374 Arias-Estero, 2015).

375 **Conclusion**

376 In recent years, within the school context, the evaluation of game performance
377 and its components has been linked to the application of pedagogical models and,
378 recently, to the hybridization of sports education and game-based approaches. Using
379 methodologies that transfer responsibility to students involved in real-game contexts
380 improves students' cognitive and physical domains by using the GPAI to evaluate their
381 learning. Moreover, it is suggested that the GPAI be used with knowledge tests to
382 confirm students' learning acquisition. It is necessary to take advantage of the benefits of
383 using technology to facilitate the implementation of GPAI through standardized software
384 by students and teachers. Future studies should explore the use of the GPAI by students
385 as evaluators and expand the use of the GPAI in more games to disseminate and extend
386 its use.

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